

International Journal of VLSI design & Communication Systems (VLSICS)

ISSN: 0976 - 1357 (Online); 0976 - 1527(print)

<https://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vlsics.html>

SCOPE OF THE JOURNAL

International Journal of VLSI design & Communication Systems (VLSICS) is a bi monthly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of VLSI Design & Communications. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on advanced VLSI Design & communication concepts and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to this journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the VLSI design & Communications.

Topics of interest

- Design
- VLSI Circuits
- Computer-Aided Design (CAD)
- Low Power and Power Aware Design
- Testing, Reliability, Fault-Tolerance
- Emerging Technologies
- Post-CMOS VLSI
- VLSI Applications (Communications, Video, Security, Sensor Networks, etc)
- Nano Electronics, Molecular, Biological and Quantum Computing
- Intellectual Property Creating and Sharing
- Wireless Communications

<https://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vlsics.html>

Members of the Editorial Board

Associate Editors

- Santosh Koppa, University of Texas at San Antonio, USA

Editorial Board Members

- Amel Ourici, University Badji Mokhtar of Annaba, Algeria
- Amir Abbas Baradaran, Azad University and Payamenoor University, Iran
- Amitabha Sinha, Indian Institute of Engineering, Science & Technology, India
- Anand Nayyar, Duy Tan University, Viet Nam
- Arman Roohi, University of Central Florida, FL, USA
- Asadollah Shahbahrami, University of Guilan, Iran
- Atena Abdi, Amirkabir University of Technology, Iran
- Barbaros Preveze, Cankaya University, Turkey
- Chien-Cheng Yu, Hsiuping University of Science and Technology, Taiwan
- Felix J. Garcia Clemente, University of Murcia, Spain
- Gayatri Mehta, University of North Texas, USA
- Hamid Ali Abed Al-asadi, Basra University, Iraq
- Hossein Khademolhosseini, Islamic Azad University, Iran
- Indranil Hatai, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, India
- Isa Maleki, Islamic Azad university, Iran
- Intisar Al-Mejibli, University of Essex, United Kingdom
- Jawad K. Ali, University of Technology, Iraq
- Joydeep Bhattacharyya, Intel, USA
- Kamaraju M, Gudlavalleru Engineering College, India
- Keivan Navi, Shahid Beheshti University, Iran
- Manjusha Pandey, Indian Institute of Information Technology, India
- Manoj Kumar, Vidya College of Engineering, India
- Manoj kumar, NIT, India
- Mohammed Atif, Arab Open University, Kuwait
- Nadia Abd-Alsabour, Cairo university, Egypt
- Mohankumar N, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, India
- Mouna Jouini, University of Tunis, Tunisia
- Naveed Farhana, College of Computers and Information Technology, Saudi Arabia,
- Nazmus Saquib, University of Manitoba, Nazmus
- Nihar Athreyas, University of Massachusetts, USA
- Omid Mahdi Ebadati E, Kharazmi University, Iran
- Pavel Loskot, Swansea University, UK
- Paulo Maciel, Center of Informatics, Federal University of Pernambuco
- Periola Ayodele, Bells University of Technology, Nigeria
- Prasanna Kumar Sahu, National Institute of Technology-Rourkela, India

<http://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vlsics.html>

- Ramtin Mohammadi-Zand, University of Central Florida, USA
- Sachin Modgil, National Institute of Industrial Engineering-Mumbai, India
- Sandip Chakraborty, Indian Institute of Information Technology Guwahati, India
- Shahid Ali, Ascent Group Of Institutes, New Zealand
- Somdip Dey, University of Essex, UK
- Subhankar Mukherjee, Samsung India Software Operations, India
- Vahideh Hayyolalam, Koç University, Turkey
- Vimal Upadhyay, Indian Institute of Information Technology-Allahabad, India,
- Vinod Pangracious, University of Pierre & Marie Curie, Sorbonne University Paris, France
- Wichian Sittiprapaporn, Mahasarakham University, Thailand
- Xue Wu, Tsinghua University, China
- Yanrong Lu, Civil Aviation University of China, China

Reviewers

- Adethya Sudarsanan, Cognizant Technology Solutions, India
- Ashraf A. Osman, California State University, USA
- Banda Sreenivas, Jyothishmathi Institute of Technology and Science, India
- Bhagyalakshmi H.R, Visvesvaraya Technological University, India
- Deepak Gupta, Jodhpur National University, India
- Deepti Garg, Panjab University, India
- Farshad Safaei, Shahid Beheshti University, Iran
- Gnana Jayanthi J, J.J.College of Engineering and Technology, India
- Gnanasekaran T, R.M.K College of Engineering and Technology, India
- Gokul, Velalar College of Engineering and Technology, India
- Gurusurthy K.S, Bangalore University, India
- Hameem Shanavas.I, MVJ College of Engineering, India
- Hemalatha M, Karpagam University, India
- Jyotsna Kumar Mandal, University of Kalyani, India
- Kishan Rao K, Vaagdevi Group of Technical Institutions, India
- Kuppusamy K, Alagappa University, India
- Kushal K S, Dr.Ambedkar Institute of Technology, India
- Majed Valadbeigi, Shahid Beheshti University, Iran
- Manpreet Singh, Punjabi University, India
- Mohan H.S, SJB Institute of Technology, India
- Monika Jain, Galgotia College of Engg. & Tech., India
- Nagendra Babu G, Indian Institute of Technology - Roorkee, India
- Navaid Zafar Rizvi, Gautam Buddha University, India
- Neeraj Kumar, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, India
- Nehru K, Institute of Aeronautical Engineering-Hyderabad, India
- Niladri Sekhar Dey, Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, India
- Nishant Doshi, National Institute of Technology - Surat, India
- Nitesh Kumar Dixit, Rajasthan Technical University, India
- Pinki Nayak, Amity School of Engg. and Technology, India

<https://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vlsics.html>

- Praveen J., PES Institute of Technology & Management, India
- Raghavendra M.V, Swathi Institute of Technology & Sciences, India
- Rahimunnisa, Karunya University, India
- Rahul Kosarwal, Oaars Corp, India,
- Rajendra Prasad Somineni, ACE Engineering College, India
- Ramesh K, Nandha Engg. College, India
- Rangaraju H G, Government Engineering College, India
- Ravilla Dilli, Manipal University, India
- Reena Dadhich, Govt. Engineering College Ajmer, India
- Reshmi Maulik, Master of Science in Information Technology, India
- Roopali Garg, Panjab University, India
- Saeid Sharifian Nia, University of Isfahan, Iran
- Samarendra Nath Sur, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Technology, India
- Sandeep Kumar Pandey, Institute of Technology & Management, GIDA, India
- Sanjay M. Koli, Smt. Kashibai Navale College of Engineering, India
- Sathishkumar P, Amrita School of Engineering, India
- Shivaling M Hunagund, Visvesvaraya Technological University, India
- Snehal Laddha, RCOEM, India
- Soheil Sarmadi, University of South Florida, USA
- Sri Rama Krishna K, V R Siddhartha Engineering College, India
- Sudarshan Patel, Gujarat Technological University, India
- Sumathi M, Sathyabama University, India
- Sumithra Devi K.A, R V College of Engineering, India
- Sumithra M.G, Bannari Amman Institute of Technology, India
- Sunil Pandey, SVNIT Surat, India
- Suresh Varma P, Adikavi Nannaya University, India
- Syed Ameer Abbas S, Mepco Schlenk Engineering College, India
- Tarasaikumar, CMR Technical Campus, India
- Tarun Kumar J, Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, India
- Thulasi Bai V, Dean/R&D, India
- Ujwala A.Belorkar, Hvpms College of Engg. & Technology, India
- Uttara Kumari, R.V.College of Engineering, India
- Valliammal N, Avinashilingam Institute for Home Science and Higher Education for Women University, India
- Varatharajan R, Bharath University, India
- Vasanth K, Sathyabama University, India
- Vasudevareddy K, Nbkrist Vidyanagar, India
- Vemu Sulochana, Centre for Development of Advanced Computing, India
- Vikas Maheshwari, Apeejay Styra University, India
- Viral Kapadia, Birla Vishwakarma Mahavidyalaya Engg College, India
- Viranjay M. Srivastava, Jaypee University of Information Technology, India

Former Editor In chief :

- Brajesh Kumar Kaushik, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, India (2010 ~ 2020)

<https://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vlsics.html>

Paper Submission & Manuscript preparation Guide

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through **Email: vlsicsjournal@airccse.org** or **vlsics@airconline.com** or through **[Submission System](#)**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal. For paper format download the template in this page

[Manuscript Template](#)

Process

Submissions are accepted for review with the understanding that the same work has been neither submitted to, nor published in, another publication. Simultaneous submission to other publications will result in immediate rejection of the paper. Papers are not within the journal scope will be rejected immediately after the pre review process.

All manuscripts will be subject to a well established, fair, unbiased peer review and refereeing procedure, and are considered on the basis of their significance, novelty and usefulness to the Journals readership. The reviewing structure will always ensure the anonymity of the referees & it will be reviewed by 3 experts in the field. The review output will be one of the following decisions:

1. Accept
2. Accept with minor changes
3. Weak Accept with major changes
4. Reject

The review process may take approximately two ~ three months to be completed. The Editor reserves the right to reject a paper if it does not meet the aims and scope of the journal, if it is not revised well.

Copy Right Form

Email the journal secretary at **vlsicsjournal@airccse.org** or **vlsics@airconline.com** to receive the copyright form

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us
: **vlsicsjournal@airccse.org** or **vlsics@airconline.com** or **vlsicsjournal@yahoo.com**

<https://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vlsics.html>

Indexing

Abstracting & Indexing Services:

The Articles of VLSICS are Indexed / Abstracted in the following index services:

Bibliographic Information

ISSN : 0976 - 1527
E-ISSN: 0976 - 1357
doi : 10.5121/vlsic

<https://aircse.org/journal/vlsi/vlsics.html>

Google Scholar Indexing

Citations 2424, h-index 25, i10-Index 69

More details

<https://scholar.google.co.in/citations?user=ZdE-aVMAAAAJ>

Cited by

[VIEW ALL](#)

	All	Since 2017
Citations	2424	1038
h-index	25	15
i10-index	69	29

<https://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vlsics.html>